

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

Policy Brief 2025/12
December 5, 2025
By Dylan Lamberti

Prescription Drug Prices for Medicaid

Issue/problem

In November, the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services announced the launch of [GENERating cost Reductions fOr U.S. Medicaid \(GENEROUS\) Model](#) to reduce prescription drug prices for Medicaid through most-favoured-nation (MFN) pricing. GENEROUS will launch in [January 2026](#) for a five-year term. In alignment with this domestic strategy, the US and UK governments announced their agreement to establish [zero tariffs](#) on UK pharmaceutical products into the US, contingent on the UK increasing the NHS's [price threshold](#) for treatments by 25%.

Description of the problem

These dual moves from the Trump administration represent an attempt to increase prices for pharmaceuticals globally while reducing them domestically, marking a strategic push to target foreign markets by the American administration to alter the MFN price point.

For instance, the Trump administration has asked drugmakers to reveal the [confidential details of contracts](#) signed with insurers in Canada, the other six members of the G7, Denmark, and Sweden as it seeks to set new MFN benchmarks, similarly using the threat of [100% tariffs on branded drugs](#). Australia is likewise [engaged in negotiations](#) with the Trump administration over its Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme, which [spent \\$17.7B in FY2024](#) to subsidize drug cost.

Results

The US-UK agreement signals a strategic shift that embeds pharmaceutical pricing demands into trade agreements to address domestic pricing concerns and underscores the ability of the American government to use the threat of economic sanction to encourage foreign governments to acquiesce to higher domestic drug prices.

Lessons learned

The American strategy of using the threat of steep tariffs to encourage concessions on higher foreign drug prices is likely to be replicated, particularly ahead of the [mandatory CUSMA review](#) that will begin in July 2026 and as the [pharmaceutical industry](#) pushes the EU to sign a similar agreement to encourage pharmaceutical companies to continue to invest in Europe.